

Using the Narratives to Investigate the Experiences of Kurdish Refugees

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Abstract

The issue of Refugees and Migration has become a high-profile political issue. I believe it is important to understand why people are forced to flee their home country. This research study attempted to advance a better understanding of the challenges and experiences of the Kurdish refugees in Finland.

The reality of the Kurdish people's situation is very challenging since they were divided into four countries and invaded by four stranger states. Most Kurdish people have political problems, lack freedom and equality, and struggle for identity, which is the main reason for seeking asylum.

Their life stories intend to explore the personal experiences of Kurdish people during the refugee procedure to put their voices at the centre of the research study. Therefore, by understanding the life experience of Kurdish refugees, it portrays the voices of faith and resistance of those people.

I conducted life story interviews with Kurdish refugees who have been living as a refugee for more than a year in Finland. Their refugee life experiences and discussions were analysed with the Listening Guide (LG) analysis method.

Introduction

In this chapter, I explore the relationship between the three concepts of belonging, community, and integration by exploring the life stories of participants' experiences. I used the Listening Guide (LG) method for analysing data collection (Gilligan, 1993; Doucet and Mauthner 2008; Woodcock, 2016). The reason LG (Brown and Gilligan, 1991) was identified as an appropriate method for analysis is that it focuses on narratives (storytelling) as opposed to listening to the participant (Brown and Gilligan, 1991). Listening Guide method analysis is a meaningful method for data analysis Of

the perspectives of the participants and explores their experiences in the context of the Belonging, Community, and Integration of Kurdish refugees in Finland. I have recognised four key narratives based on the life stories approach of participants' experiences. The following subsection will explore significant areas of language that participants experienced as important concerning belonging, community, and integration. The role of language:

- Language for Integration
- Language for access to information and services
- The role of education
- Social capital competencies

These are the first themes that I will discuss in the first chapter. The first narrative, "Belonging, Community, and Integration", echoes a composite of explanations from participants in which they significantly talk about belonging, community, and integration and their own progress in this field. This chapter will discuss this narrative and explore participants' understanding of belonging, community, and integration and also the contributions of all the participants' experiences in this study. In this identification and exploration, I investigate the participants' life stories approach and also the research relevant to an investigation of this narrative. I connect the understanding and dignity of Kurdish to be refugees and starting a new life in Finland, the connection of belonging, community, and integration to the refugee concept and identify and understand the aims of the participants through chapter discussion. I investigate the data and re-building of participants' life stories to clarify and understand their experiences. This challenge is met by developing an epistemological and ontological framework that focuses on understanding and knowledge creation, negotiated in order to gain access to identity, modification, and meaning of life story experience as related to the research subject (McAdams 1999). This research study analysis is based on the Listening Guide method to analyse the interview transcriptions. The expression of the plot and I-poems forms part of the first and second Listening Guide steps and citation, which is a part of narrative (story) analysis (Woodcock, 2016). The plot, I-poems, and citations adapt to the participant's flow of conversation and allow the researcher to hear the participant's voice and consider making changes in the terms of the interview (Gilligan et al., 2006). A plot and I-poem and citation were built for each of the 15 participants' experiences within the research

study. All participants had experienced the refugee process and the LG (listening for plot and I-poem and citation) describes those participants understood belonging community, and integration.

For refugees, it is imperative to foster a good relationship to belonging, community, and integrating into a diverse world in the new country. Belonging, community, and integration are complex issues within the particular context of the refugee integration process. For a successful refugee, belonging, community, and integration show benefits for the development of economic, social, educational, health, and cultural freedom in the host countries (De Haas, 2005). Belonging and integration themes are oriented toward training around cultural knowledge, work, and language skills. Belonging, community, and integration also focus on building human capital.

The opportunities for belonging, community, and integration in Finland pose several challenges that can be attributed to acquiring language skills, educational and professional qualifications, networking, and ineffective belonging and integration procedures. In the context of these concepts, the participants' life story interviews revealed the importance of learning a new language in the host country, as well as proper and adequate language, education, and social capital. According to Riessman (1993) and Gergen (2001). Language reflects how the human agency creates and maintains the social world. Also, Wachterhauser (1986 P:31) explained that language is the 'medium within which we move and understand ourselves and world from various perspective.'

A research study in Finland suggested that belonging, community, and integration are long processes, in which learning a new language is the first step. The study implied a significant need for various types of education regarding the cultural distance between the current and previous home country (MacGilleon, 2017). Understanding the refugee's belonging, community, and integration process is a challenging task and is related to the refugee's social capital, such as the role of human capital and integrability in the host country. The belonging, community, and integration process is one of the most complex issues attributed to the particular nuances relevant to social belonging, community, and integration. Moreover, enhancing the integration processes, such as refugee belonging, community and integration process, and

learning language, requires professional work, education, and so on (Coley et al.,2019).

The Role of Language

The participants' life stories and experiences are represented with a citation along with those of researchers who have similar views related to the subject of the chapter to afford a better understanding of belonging, community, and integration. Most participants agree that language learning is a positive thing in a new country. Research has confirmed interest in studies in the field of refugees and migration.

Learning a new language is important because the ability to communicate encourages people to discover other cultures and societies. In turn, discovering new cultures helps to change the right views and attitudes, as well as acknowledge belonging, community, and being integrated into other cultures. As such, a refugee must learn the language of the new culture to reinforce integration (Muliro, 2019). Social belonging and integration can facilitate a cohesive cultural, community, and personal level experience in the lifeworld approach (Habermas, 1987). According to Kerka (2002), trauma and adult learning are associated, as individuals with past trauma experiences are challenged in learning a new language.

Shno's, one of the participants, life story experience discussed learning the Finnish language to allow her to understand the new community and culture. She maintains her own belonging and community for integration by learning a new language. She describes her experience in the following saying.

'I began attending Finnish language classes to learn the language. I felt that it would make my life so much easier. I felt that my young age and light skin colour would make it easier for me to integrate and live amongst Finnish people. It is so much easier to adapt to a new culture when you are young. I also met other asylums and got to learn and understand their cultural backgrounds... Whenever I met Kurdish families in Finland, I felt happy and alive again. But I never gave up and decided to study the language harder to integrate and familiarise myself with the culture.'

Peshava is another participant who shared his life story experience he wants to maintain a strong sense of belonging to his indigenous community in a variety of ways. During the refugee and migration process, he experienced many unpleasant experiences based on which he encouraged other Kurdish refugees and migrants by learning the language and getting to know and understand the new culture and society. Peshava is a very strong-willed person because, although he continues to face post-stress trauma and severe physical disability, he describes his painful past as a bright light because it taught him to believe in his own power. He managed to retain his own belonging with political activities as he stepped into a new community help to create better integration for himself and another Kurdish refugee. He describes his experience in the following discussion.

'I was someone who loved the Kurdish culture. I would always try to embrace it in any way I could. For example, I would fight for Kurdish rights in debates, I would wear Kurdish clothing when possible and, generally, I was known as someone who was an active nationalist.... I started attending a language school to learn the Finnish language as soon as possible. I think I managed to integrate into the Finnish culture very early on because I was committed to building a new life for myself and my family. Being a refugee is not easy. They need to understand where we come from as each country has their issues, and each person has their problems. I want to get more politically involved and help Kurdish people to better integrate with the Finnish culture.'

Kamran, another participant, described his life story experience about integration into a new community by learning the language and understanding the community better. In the following discussion, he explains his experience related to the issue.

'We faced our first problems with integrating to a new country. Finland is a country of development and opportunities, but it's always hard when you move to a new country where you cannot speak the language. It's like a wall that is in front of you, and it is not able to let you move on. Language barriers were one of the first problems we faced. To solve these sorts of issues, individuals must work hard. Problems are like a major sea and to solve those issues you have to know how to swim. If you become

a good swimmer you can swim across easily and succeed. One of the first problems we had in Finland was not knowing the language, and not knowing how to integrate into a new country.'

Kaveh is another participant who shared his experiences and reasons for being a refugee and moving to Finland. The conflict in the Kurdistan area makes life difficult for people without international protection. The refugees encounter a tough experience as they have to face very many difficulties. He wants to own belonging by trying to integrate into the new community. I have represented Kaveh`s sharing of his life story experience with a quote from his conversation.

'My first years in Finland were very difficult and I would often be at home doing nothing. I have coped with life in Finland. I know we have cultural differences with Finland, but I have learned to accept the differences in religion, family, and lifestyle. Finnish people need to change their perception of refugees. They should help the refugees to integrate better.'

According to Toivanen`s (2013, p:30) research study, "multilingual performances of belonging". The Kurdish people speak various native dialects, and the majority are bilingual or multilingual and are integrated into the countries where they reside. In addition, related to Kurdish history background, multilingualism can be considered as a "part of who I am" and a positive value for the future of refugees in Finland.

Refugee belonging, community, and integration are common challenges encountered by immigrants within a new culture and society because of their multifaceted approach. The integration process has shown an association with the refugee experience and language skill knowledge in the host country. The feeling of belonging to a community and integration enhances the feeling of responsibility and 'the idea of belonging is central to the understanding of how people give meaning to their lives' (Marsh et al., 2007, p:7) as well as is based on common diversity. Belonging, community, and integration are concepts applied to understand the changing connection of the refugee in terms of perspective and goal to foster a relationship with the host country (Penninx and Garcés-Mascreñas, 2016).

Mustafa, another participant, shared his life story experience during the interview conversation. Mustafa was disappointed and unhappy that he had to forcefully seek refuge and pursue his future dream in another country. The control and discrimination

that he witnessed and experienced were ignorant of human rights and needs. Mustafa was worried about what will happen to his family and himself in the future. He discussed belonging and pain which must be overcome for their children for a better life and integrate into in new community. The following represents his life story experience with an extract from his conversation. He speaks.

'My generation must discuss the pain and issues they have had from the past to solve them and get over them... I've tried to keep my cultural beliefs separate from my children's lives and adapt to a much more European culture. I want my children to have a normal life. Understanding refugee integration is the common challenge to face within a new culture and society because it is a multifaceted approach.'

Learning a new language is important because the ability to communicate encourages people to discover other cultures and societies. In turn, discovering new cultures help to change the right views and attitudes, as well as acknowledge belongingness to other cultures. As such, it is imperative that a refugee learns the language of the new culture to reinforce integration (Muliro, 2019).

Belonging, community, and integration can be viewed as important development regarding bonding with society and culture based on diverse features. Therefore, belonging, community and integration are important parts of the refugee and migrant process. The consequences of belonging, community, and integration have been inferred to depend on ethnically diverse societies and cultures (Permoser and Rosenberger, 2012).

According to Warriner (2015), language learning and a sense of belonging are associative concepts for migrant and refugee groups. Language learning demonstrates ongoing challenges corresponding with the refugee population because of educational background and traumatised past. According to Little (2019), multilingual people have explicit powerful emotional priorities for one language over another. Correspondingly, there is a need for an understanding that belonging, community and integration is a multi-step process because the belonging, community and integration of refugees and immigrants require much more than just language skills and a job. The belonging, community, and integration will be incomplete and

inadequate if only language skills and work qualifications are measured because most of the refugees have different educational backgrounds and human capital. This disparity can be attributed to military conflicts, ignorance towards human rights and discrimination, political involvement in the Kurdistan area, and thus, not being able to acquire equal education.

Research studies have shown that belonging, community, and integration is an important factor for personal health and well-being (Kitchen et al., 2012). According to Anthias (2006), belonging, community, and belonging 'involves an important affective dimension relating to social bonds and ties' (Anthias, 2006, p: 21). Furthermore, Marsh suggested that networking in the host community helps accord a "social identity" to the individual (Marsh et al., 2007, p: 4). Erikson (1950) presented the idea of individualistic societies, which increase his or her unique identity. In collectivist societies, identity is described by social groups such as family, culture, and community. According to Schweitzer et al., (2005), social identity is involved in damage to the values, behaviour, identity, and principles of the hosts. Kunz (1981) and Loescher (1992) suggested that shared social identity between refugees and hosts will lead to accepting positive attitudes towards refugees. Similarly, a participant, Kamal, shared his experience of diversity in the social construct between his native country and the host country. He discussed his cultural belonging, and the environment connected to integrating into a new community with their cultural values. Finland has many positive and good points but also needs to consider the point of view about refugees in their country. The following represents Kamal's discussion of his life story experience.

'The environment I lived in Kurdistan is completely different to the environment I live in now. Finland is culturally and socially very different to where I come from. When asylums come to Europe, they are very different people with heavy and deep struggles. Finland is a democratic country where humanity exists, people have human rights, and everyone can have a say. We grew up in a country where none of these mattered. Therefore, the cultural shock is major. The freedom people have in Finland is something we've never seen in our own country... In my opinion, the first generation of immigrants will have a lot of problems when settling into a new culture. Their past and issues they've dealt with will have a direct impact in their new life....

But we all still need to work harder to integrate and change our old thought patterns.... Finland still is a very closed country. They don't allow other cultures and customs to enter their country and integrate with their own cultures. We can see a small rise of immigrants working and being integrated into the Finnish culture, but it is still a minority.'

Gulzar is another participant, and she shared her life story experience of belonging, community and learning a new language for a better life in the new society. She described her experience as.

'I managed to learn to speak the Finnish language almost fluently, although I think learning a new language is not easy for someone who hasn't lived in the country most of their life. Learning a new language requires a lot of time... I feel proud that I'm Kurdish. I can speak five languages fluently and I'm also politically active for my country.'

Based on participants' experiences, language plays an important role in the context of social empowerment in refugee life situations because the individual designs language skills as a self-empowering tool that can influence belonging and integration into a new community. So, living in a society with diverse cultural backgrounds is very challenging (Hodgins, 2018). European societies are increasingly being characterised by cultural diversity (Paola and Brunello, 2016). Correspondingly, language is an essential tool for communication and dialogue in a diverse society and offers an opportunity for own belonging and community in assisting with integration (Paola and Brunello, 2016).

Farshad, another study participant, had a very hard experience and, therefore, he tries to help Kurdish people and Finnish people to know each other, to help Kurdish refugees to integrate and adapt to the new culture better, as well as give correct information about Kurdish culture to Finnish people. The following discussion represents his life story experience.

'I started to get more involved with the community around me. I started a Kurdish association to help Kurdish and Finnish people to know and understand each better. I would go around Finnish schools to introduce and educate Finnish students with Kurdish culture and customs. I would also arrange Kurdish evening events and parties where people could talk to each other and have a good time together.... I managed to create a change. I introduced Kurdish people to

so many Finnish people and changed so many other areas and we were considered important by other Finnish societies... I think it's important for all of us to build a community together. I have personally helped Kurdish people to integrate and adapt to the culture better. In my opinion, integrating into society is different for different people.... Understanding a language as well as a culture can help anyone to understand and integrate into a new culture much faster.'

Language for Integration

Learning the language of the host country can unlock opportunities for successful belonging, community, integration, and accessibility to access services, such as healthcare, education, and social care. Integrating allows refugees and migrants to participate at the same level as natives and work together to build cohesiveness in the new community. Learning a new language is important because language skills protect mental health, promote new social resources, and increase the sense of coherence, integrating strategies that affect belonging community, and integration of the refugee in the host country (Beiser and Hou, 2001).

Successful refugee and migrant integrations have been shown to generate opportunities for development towards economic, cultural, and social improvement of the host countries. However, integration is a complex issue that warrants an improved understanding of the general process of social integration. These can be augmented with the building of human capital. Refugees need a combination of the old and new cultures in a new society to facilitate the integrating process with their own culture and conflict of cultural integration to the new culture and society (Valtonen, 1990).

New language learning can offer a key gateway to integration because it provides an ability to obtain information towards the improvement and development of new experiences in a new circumstance. Language learning increases the ability to promote individual autonomy and motivation in a new culture and society (Pablo et al., 2015). According to Imberti (2007), language is a key for a person's conformity, because of the person being able to make explicit emotions and feelings and tell stories about themselves and the environment, and transport messages and knowledge.

According to Morrice (2019), language functions as both the important key and barrier role for refugees. Therefore, refugee people want to learn a new language to help facilitate their integration into the host country. This necessitates understanding the refugees' voices and encouraging them to find positive ways to address their own needs and work towards integrating into Finnish society.

The following is a discussion of the I - poem of the Listening Guide method used to express the participants' experiences. Zakaria, as a participant, talked about his experience in the life story interview and discussed that language learning is necessary for integration and work in the host country. Zakaria's life story presented similar experiences to the other participants. The following represents the participants' conversation with me regarding their involvement with social integration with an I-poem derived from their life story interview discussion.

Zakaria

I learnt the language

I am working.

I am suffering from leg pain

I try to integrate myself to Finnish society and culture

I have learnt a lot of good things here

I was very young when

I left my country

Shno

I remember

I did not understand the written text

I learnt the language.

I learnt to understand

Peshava

I managed to find a Finnish-speaking job within two years.

I think I managed to integrate

I was committed to building a new life

I did not want us to go over

I noticed a big difference

I made the decision

Mahabad

I started learning

I felt free and reborn

I was calm and felt freedom

I had never felt before

I entered felt very different

I came from

I felt very happy and content

I would have endless conversations

I was part of a community

I would never ask too many

I would just accept

I was very eager to learn

I would always try

I learnt something

Gulzar

I managed to learn the language

I was surrounded by supportive people

I got to know people from all over the world

I also met people from Africa

I remember that they would place their hand on top of my head

I did not understand what they were trying to say

I slowly learnt to speak the language

Farshad

I began a new journey in Finland

I began learning Finnish language

I then joined a college named Christian College

I began studying again

I studied hard and wanted to

I was not successful

I think one of the reasons for

I wasn't guided throughout

I was treated similarly to Finnish people

I was expected to have the same level of

I was left without additional help

I would have needed

Mansur

I began a new life in Finland

I began studying the language

I learnt to speak

I was fluent enough

I moved to a bigger city

I lived in this new city

I was able to find work

I also did some studying

I studied to become an electrician

Karim

I made was to learn the language

I could start a new life

I wanted to make a difference

I learnt to speak the language

I started going to language classes

I went to extra private language

I had an entry exam to study

I was accepted

I graduated with a master's degree

I applied for a course to become a translator

Hemin

I tried to learn the language

I developed a very good social network

I learnt to speak the language

I have only used a translator twice

I moved to Finland

I request to see a therapist

Savbolāgh

I was sent to a language

I had only seen in movies

I had to mix this with my world

I won the battle

I was able to mix my own culture with the Finnish culture

I really tried to live a good life

Language for Access to Information and Services

According to Norredam (2011), based on cultural barriers, refugees encounter challenges in accessing the right healthcare information and barriers involving care delivery due to a lack of cultural competence among health providers. The research study investigated refugees and migrants and found that they have a poor understanding of the primary healthcare system.

The refugee experience of integrating into Finnish society is riddled with difficulties, the conflict between people of different ethnic groups causes isolation from Finnish society. It is, thus, important to create space for diversity and multiplicity based on the

thoughts, feelings, and prospects of others, as an all-inclusive approach. Parekh developed the theory of multiculturalism as a “perspective on human life”, which addresses multicultural societies by the convenient structure of the constitution, group delegation, justice and rights based on national and cultural identity, education, intercultural interaction, and gender relations (Parekh, 2000).

In order to rebuild and reinforce the integration of refugees and migrants into Finnish society, the country should encourage private investment in employing immigrants. Finland has not been able to leverage and optimise the employment value of refugees and migrants. Finland’s social structures are different from other OECD countries, thereby, making the integration of refugees and migrants difficult (Lindström, 2018).

The Kurdish refugees’ experiences show that a low level of general literacy and health literacy can act as a barrier to their health information and skill. Moreover, the ongoing military conflict in the Kurdistan region limits equal access to education and information. Mansur, another of the participants, explained that it is difficult to understand the medical terms in the Finnish language because of the language barrier, thereby limiting healthcare access. He mentioned the requirement to know more about medical terms and treatment in his language. The following represents his experience derived from his life story experience.

‘I began studying the language.... I was fluent enough to take care of my own business and did not require a translator to help me... Unfortunately, I did not understand all the terms in Finnish. Understanding my illness in Kurdish helped me to take care of myself better.’

Karim, one of the participants, explained that he grew up in tough political conditions and saw and experienced multiple problems in the Kurdistan region. This experience motivated him to decide to initiate changes and move to a better place for a better future. Multiculturalism has been one of the greatest success life stories experiences and constitutes a significant Kurdish national identity. Discrimination, lack of necessary human rights, as well as the political and military conflicts in Kurdistan are reasons that the majority of young, aged Kurds cannot find a place to study and work, leading to their escape. Many of them are energetic and capable individuals who can contribute to employment and the economy (Kuzu 2015). Karim discussed how learning the language gave him a chance to manage and build a new life and work.

'I tried to learn the language so that I could start a new life and find my place in this new society. I wanted to make a difference in my own life. Learning a new language helps an individual to find a job.... I helped with translating and guided refugees to settle in Finland...

I participated in events and speaking opportunities to discuss multi cultures so that I could help Finnish people to get to know us immigrants better.'

The integration process is related to building relationships with new roles in the new society. For a refugee, it is crucial to gain an understanding of the integration resources, such as multicultural capital and skills. The refugee integration processes involve mainstream social activities and cultural diversity in the new society. Refugees, as such, essentially need to learn the language of the host country as that facilitates communication with other people and helps gain awareness of the new environment. Language learning also helps establish a social identity which, in turn, helps the refugee integrate into the new community. Language learning empowers a person to express their own emotional and spiritual feelings (Thomas et al., 2016).

Hemin is another study participant who suffered and experienced significant pain in their home country, and, during the refugee process, he kept all pain and suffering a secret in his heart and never spoke to anyone in his family or his best friend until he arrived in Finland as a refugee. He had to rebuild and learn to heal and when he learned the Finnish language properly, he could explain it in his own words to the therapist and so he managed to recover in Finland.

'I tried to learn the language as fluently as possible. I developed a very good social network.

After six months of living in Finland, I learnt to speak the language fluently. I also developed a good network with various Finnish people... I asked to see a therapist again. I discussed everything from my childhood and everything else that happened in between until the present day. This time seeing a therapist had two benefits. The first one was that, because my language was much better, I did not need a translator, so I was confident enough to discuss my problems with my own language without any help. Second was that I learnt to speak with calm.'

The importance of mother language learning is undeniable for identification. According to Maalouf (2016), 'Language is the axis of cultural identity whereas pluralism of language is the axis of all pluralities' (Maalouf, 2016, p.19). A research study in Australia and Austria showed acculturative stress to be a factor in the migration process. So, the process of integrating into a new culture needs to maintain a balance between the indigenous culture and identity of both the refugee and host country (Kartal and Kiropoulos, 2016).

Savbolāgh, a study participant, explained she tried to learn the language because she wanted to gain a better understanding of the host's cultural values and help their children integrate into a new culture and environment.

'...we had language difficulties... My husband and I were sent to language school to learn the Finnish language. Life often forces us to adapt to events that occur. Although our environment was the complete opposite to our culture...'

Singleton and Krause (2009) claim that lower levels of literacy influence health status and such individuals demonstrate a limited understanding of medical information that is presented in the language of the host country. More specifically, the health literate in their language can be less health literate in the host country. There is a need to 'Meet the needs of education systems affected by conflict, national calamities, and instability and conduct educational programs in ways that promote mutual understanding, peace, and tolerance, and help to prevent violence and conflict' (UNESCO, 2000 p: 197).

The Role of Education

There are multiple advantages of education in the integration process of migrants: Firstly, education reduces the concerns encompassing economics. Secondly, enhanced knowledge and ability to interpret information allow them a better understanding of an unknown environment. Education has been shown to lead to a positive attitude toward refugees and migrants. 'Education transmits norms of tolerance and equality, it might foster humanitarian and egalitarian sentiments among the native population, combating cultural and racial prejudices' (Paola and Brunello,

2016, p. 31). According to a UNHCR (2011) global review, access to education for refugees is more difficult for girls than for boys: the report explained that education can build important facilities for refugees in terms of social integration in host countries. 'Satisfies basic learning needs and enriches the lives of learners and their overall experience of living' (UNHCR, 2009, p. 22).

The refugees need to access education in their new country because most of them arrive with very little previous education, as well as their higher qualifications obtained from their native country are not recognised in the host country. Many Kurdish children have been observed to drop out before finishing school because of military conflict in the Kurdistan areas based on the participants' experiences and their data from the life story interviews. Education is very important to build a better world and valuable employment opportunities to change the life situation. This consequence about the role of education is supported by Sho's story and other participants have similar experiences, as represented by I -poems from their life story experiences they shared with me.

Shno

I was able to attend school.

I graduated with good grades.

I never gave up on studying

I did not understand the written text

I learnt the language,

I learnt to understand

I began attending Finnish language

I decided to study further

I would study in the mornings and in the evenings

I started to be interested in becoming a beautician

I graduated as a beautician

Research investigation into migrants' health literacy revealed that language skills, education levels, age, and sex, impact health literacy in migration and refugee situations. It is important to understand that education and literacy impact the refugees'

successful experiences in the host countries (Lee and Kang, 2018). Peshava discussed in the life story interview that he had a challenging experience with education in his home country which affected his life. The following represents his life story experience with an I -poem which developed from our discussion.

Peshava

I ran in the dark
I fell into the (Tenor)oven.
My face, chest and hands were all burned
I will never forget
I learnt to adapt
I was good at school
I kept studying
I was trying to replace
I was one of the best students
I felt like the other students
I decided to start a handwriting
I wasn't able to study
I didn't make
I had to stop studying
I really wanted to study
I loved arts
I really wanted to study again

Access to education is a principal human right and denotes a significant value in highlighting the cultural and social identity of refugees in the host country. According to Nicolai and Triplehorn (2003), education can provide several forms of protection, related to psychological and emotional well-being, termed “psychosocial protection,” and to learning, termed “cognitive protection”. Mahabad, one of the participants, explained her life story experience and how learning a language and a new society

helped her to understand and recognise herself and deal with problems. The following I-poem formed from her life story experience expresses this issue.

Mahabad

I decided not to continue my studies

I did not enjoy it

I did not feel motivated to continue

I moved to north of Finland

I started learning

I felt free and reborn

I was very eager to learn

I knew

I had learnt was not enough

I attended a course

I was expected to start

I studied

I tried to learn alone

I had to stand with

The refugees need the tools of knowledge and education skills to guide them into a stepwise integration within the host country. The refugees and migrants create new challenges to successfully navigate this route of value transfer and social role for adapting to a new society (Binder and Toši, 2005). Therefore, according to OECD (2019), the successful integration of refugees can help create social capacity, reduce conflicts with new societies and build equality into societies. Gulzar had a hard life story experience; she has faced many different situations that she said she can never forget. So, understanding the refugee process reflects the refugees' ability to cultivate themselves in a new culture and society. Gulzar explained her life story experience in the following I-poem which emerged from her experience shared with me.

Gulzar

I went to school for eight years

I had to drop out

I had always wanted to move

I managed to learn the language

I slowly learnt to speak the language

I had studied English in Syria

I loved studying

I chose sociology

I really enjoyed school

I wasn't fluent in Finnish language

I managed to learn to speak Finnish

I think learning a new language

I learnt to speak Finnish

I can speak five languages

I've also studied a little bit of music

Refugees intend to create a future for themselves based on a good education motivated by complex situations during the refugee journey. Most of the refugees were deprived of the basic right to education due to several different reasons in the home country. The following discussion represents the life story experience of Kamal, another participant, in an I-poem created from sharing his experience.

Kamal

I have studied until primary school

I had to stop going to school

I got involved

I moved to Finland

I am still politically active

I try to help my people

I hope to see a change

I hope that one day Finland

I think Finnish people see us migrants

The traumatic experience of becoming a refugee affects the mental health and well-being of a person and is precipitated to future generations (Bezo and Maggie, 2015). A research study in Sweden showed that family trauma among refugees showed considerably high levels of trauma indication (Daud et al., 2008). The research investigations found refugee parents' trauma was related to negative psychological consequences among their children (Vaage et al., 2011). As such, the mother's trauma manifested as mental health symptoms, emotional distress, and behavioural problems among adolescent children. The effects of trauma on refugees have been studied to be long-lasting and disruptive, both internally and externally (Steel et al., 2006). The refugee families encountered several difficult experiences and warranted access to education to stimulate relevant activities to relieve difficulties in their everyday lives. According to Handlin (1951), the refugees suffer multiple losses, including social identity, livelihood, place, family, friends, and support systems, as well as the struggle to discover the way in a new culture and society which is often projected in an unfriendly and environment with unfamiliar language and customs. Understanding of cultural diversity is important in a host country because it encourages refugees to build a new start. Farshad described his experience in the following I – poem developed from his conversation with me.

Farshad

I completed high school in Baghdad

I wasn't able to graduate
I had to drop out
I began a new journey in Finland
I began learning Finnish language
I then joined a college
I began studying again
I studied hard
I wasn't guided throughout
I was treated similarly to Finnish students
I noticed a journalism course
I was really interested in
I am quite talented
I can speak multiple languages
I decided to go back to school
I graduated
I started a Kurdish association to help Kurdish
I would go around Finnish schools

The state of anti-democratic governments in which Kurds are living has an impact on Kurdish students' learning and education conditions. The mother tongue is useless in the education system, Kurdish students often stop studying after the primary level. According to the research study on education and identity, it is suggested that Kurds make the right decision to have education in their mother tongue because education can help to build up a new identity and "the rebuilding of Kurdishness" in the contemporary world (Beltekin, 2016, p: 31). Mansour is another participant and

described why he left school in the home country and did not go back. The following is his discussion I-poem constructed from the life story experience shared with me.

Mansour

I studied until fifth grade

I had a normal life

I then realised

I was a Kurd

I had a responsibility

I was ready to become a Peshmerga

I was young

I continued

I then decided

I was in danger

I moved to Finland

I began studying the language

I learnt to speak

I was fluent enough

I also did some studying

I studied to become an electrician

I stopped studying

The use of the Kurdish language in education is prevented and education rights are weak. Education plays an important role in human identity. Many research investigations explained that education is important to accept the direction of

modernisation. According to Çayır and Gürkaynak's investigation, education focuses on information on human rights and principles of democracy in society (Çayır and Gürkaynak, 2008).

Karim is another participant who described his experience in the refugee process and how to get opportunities in the host country. The following I-poem developed from his life story experience with me and illustrates his discussion.

Karim

I went to school in age of six.

I studied in my hometown

I was brought up

I remind myself to think

I was a student

I always felt sad

I should have studied it in my own language

I would often debate

I worked with a political group

I had to move out to

I'm young

I have the ability to change

I wanted to build a new future

I moved to Finland

I thought my past and the new beginning

I made was to learn the language

I wanted to make a difference

I learnt to speak the language

I started going to language classes

I went to extra private language

I graduated with a master's degree

I worked for the Refugee Centre

I was expected to study for my PhD degree

I graduated to become a teacher

I have also written various articles

I wrote my first novel called "Kurdish and Guns, to be or not to be".

I translated a book from Finnish to Kurdish called "Ihmisiä Ihmisiä"

I translated books from Finnish to Kurdish.

I wrote a novel in Kurdish called "Nan VA Azadi"

I tried to turn Kurdish dreams and thoughts

I described

I wrote about religion politics, immigrants, multicultural difficulties

I have lectured

The participants' life stories and experiences show a high level of educational influence on their life situation in the host country because the educational backgrounds are varied, Kurdistan's political situation has affected many aspects of Kurdish people's life and their education level. According to Budwig (2015), education is an important channel for communication and successful integration in a host country. Hemin is another participant who has experienced unpleasant situations in

his home country and has started a new life. The following represents his life story experience in an I-poem developed from his discussion with me.

Hemin

I was always politically active
I enjoyed studying
I was one of the best students
I studied well
I participated in various competitions
I would always get a really good grade
I was able to memorise all of the Quran
I was interested in the Kurdish language
I was also able to read
I loved reading books
I used to walk and read books
I was very keen on comedy
I will become the next Charlie Chaplin
I studied acting
I was very happy
I enjoyed
I also really enjoyed history and geography
I left school
I stayed in the mountains
I was only 15 years
I learnt fast and quickly
I become one of the best students
I was sad
I used to read books

- I enjoyed
- I moved to Finland
- I tried to learn the language
- I developed a very good social network
- I learnt to speak the language
- I request to see a therapist.
- I did not feel safe
- I applied to study at a university
- I applied to study politics

Social capital competencies

In this section, I explain the understanding of the role of social capital in Kurdish refugees' experiences and competencies for belonging, community, and integration. For expressiveness in the section, I have given three examples of Kurdish refugees who have become famous in the host country by which they can serve as useful guides and role models in this field.

Social capital has a positive role in the refugee situation, such as language ability, education skills, acculturation variables, social connections, and different kinds of social networks (Cheung and Phillimore, 2013). Putnam (2000) noted the decline in the contribution of social capital as the very fabric of the connections with each leading to impoverished lives and communities. Therefore, social capital implies social groups, interpersonal relationships, identity, understanding, norms, values, trust, cooperation, and reciprocity. Putnam (2000) suggested social capital is a key element in establishing and maintaining democracy. They explained the two concepts of social capital, and bonding and bridging to be relevant to the social network with different groups of people, thus highlighting the benefits of social capital for society (Putnam 2000). According to Ellison et al., (2007), social capital development in today's age is evident on the internet via social networking websites. For example, Facebook bridges capital through "virtual" social capital. Social capital refers to the network of social connections with reference to doing good for other people. Therefore, the social

network provides a channel for performing good deeds, as well as related to health and welfare. Personal sociability can also be connected to kinship and friendship (Putnam, 2000, p. 19). Bourdieu (1972) illuminated that social networks are elements that associate the refugee population with the new society and social capital, thus rendering them the availability to utilise those resources in social networks. The social capital of refugees is having more important friends. The refugees have different kinds of social networks and access different types of social capital, which has a positive impact on the integration and acculturation in the host country (Cheung and Phillimore, 2013) According to Foley and Edwards (1998), an explanation of social capital is inventing collected from networks. The following represents a Kurdish refugee from a Finnish local newspaper (Ilta-Sanomat, 2020) who tries to have a good relationship and network with Finnish people. He spoke.

Kurdish Photographic in Finland Helsinki supersized a photographic exhibition for a Finnish friend whose action as a refugee in Finland was a good social network connection. A photo exhibition was arranged in the middle of the Helsinki forest and the background of the beautiful story was the friendship of Kurdish and Finnish men. A Finnish friend had a stroke two years ago and his hobby was photography. His good friend Rasoul Khorram surprised him by building his exhibition in the middle of the forest. Khorram explained when his friend walks along the bridge in the forest, accompanied by his photographs, his eyes get wet.

Putnam (2000) explained that social connection has been continually evolving during the last century, such as the change in competencies for informal and formal communication. Social capital has a different meaning and value for each society and pertains to functioning through social groups for understanding competencies for norms, values, trust, cooperation, and reciprocity involving relationships in the larger diverse groups in the community. According to Portes (1998), social capital is seen as a factor that helps resolve all problems. The main idea is that 'social networks are valuable' (Putnam, 2000, p: 206).

On the same lines, Shno, another participant, explained the difference between her native country and the social connections in Finland. The following is from her life story experience shared with me. She explains.

'In our culture in Iran, neighbours take care of each other when needed. Her reaction made me realise how different our cultures were. I learnt that Finnish culture was the complete opposite of ours. It made me feel very lonely and isolated.'

Similarly, another participant, Kamal, explained the change in the surrounding environment. The following shows her life story experience in a quote formed from her experience shared with me.

'The environment I lived in Kurdistan is completely different to the environment I live in now. Finland is culturally and socially very different to where I come from. When asylum seekers come to Europe, they are very different people with heavy and deep struggles.'

Putnam (1995, p. 77) talked about the technology "individualising" via the increase in mediums like television and the Internet, suspecting that 'virtual reality helmets will carry this further in the future.' Through these new "virtual reality" helmets, technology is driving a wedge between our individual and collective interests. Putnam (1995) suggests that aspects of technology cause changes in social equality.

The Kurds of Finland are working towards improving the living conditions for themselves and others with good competencies for belonging, community, and integration. This can be attributed to the fact that the social capital of a person refers to the ability, knowledge, and awareness to create sociality and good network relationships. Bourdieu (1972) illuminated several forms of social capital, such as physical capital, political capital, and symbolic capital. Farshad, another participant in the life story experience, explained that he encourages the Kurdish and Finnish people to come together to develop good social networks and relationships. The following quote is taken from his life story experience shared with me.

'I started to get more involved with the community around me. I started a Kurdish association to help Kurdish and Finnish people to know and understand each other better. I would go around Finnish schools to introduce and educate Finnish students about Kurdish culture and customs. I would also arrange Kurdish evening events and parties where people could talk to each other and have a good time together.'

According to Hanifan (1916), social capital relates to the common activities of daily life, such as friendship, empathy, a sense of purpose, and communication between neighbours. Social capital affects a dramatic improvement in the quality of life in belonging, community, and integration. Putnam (1993) suggested that social capital can be a valuable tool in combating many social failures in modern societies, such as crime.

Kamal, one of the participants in the life story experience, explained the evolving experiences of political events and related regulations in the context of the available resources for building social capital in a new community. He is happy and hopeful for the second generation will not face many problems. The following is from his life story experience shared with me.

'The first generation of immigrants will have a lot of problems when settling into a new culture. Their past and the issues they've dealt with will have a direct impact on their new life. It is much easier for the second generation to cope and settle down in a new country. Growing up in a country where they can learn the language early on will have a big positive impact on their life. They are not a victim of their memories and past lives....'

The social capital concept of the refugee correlates with integration in the new community because the refugees and migrants need information and knowledge for the building of social trust in the new community. According to Smith and Baltes (1997), the inclusion and belonging of refugees to social networks and social relationships help them in different ways. The refugees need to build a social capital connection and relationship networks of trust and reciprocity between groups and communities (Griffiths et al., 2005). According to Dasgupta (2002), social capital comprises social norms and network connections for understanding benefits, which help improve the efficiency of society. The development of human capital in the concept of education and health increases the positive growth of social capital. Caucher Birkar is another Kurdish refugee, and he is a good example of human and social capital. The following explanation from his website highlights this situation.

Caucher Birkar from asylum seeker to Fields Medal winner in (2018) at Cambridge, UK. He grew up Kurdish in Iran and now lives in England. He moved to the UK as a refugee in 2000. He

explains that not easy to be a Kurd a famous says the Kurds have no friends other than the mountains. Birkar said after receiving his award from the International Congress of Mathematicians "I'm hoping that this news will put a smile on the faces of those 40 million Kurds around the world.

Putnam (2000) explained that social movements and social capital have a close connection by which a social network is created and extends the resources for this social capital and social movement (Putnam, 2000). Behrouz Boochani is another Kurdish refugee and another example of human and social capital. The following discussion from his website represents and highlights his refugee experience.

Behrouz Boochani is an Iranian Kurdish writer and journalist. He was born in Ilam, a Kurdish homeland in western Iran. He has been in the Manus Island detention centre in Papua New Guinea since 2013. He wrote his biography under the name of, No Friend but the Mountains in the Manus Refugee Camp in Australia, he won the Victorian Prize for Literature and the Victorian Premier's Prize for Nonfiction in 2019. He tapped out on his mobile phone.

Conclusion

In this chapter, I have investigated a discussion about Kurdish refugees' life stories and experiences in the narrative of belonging, community, and integration. The understandings of belonging, community, and integration have presented a new meaning and shed new academic insight into the participants' life story experiences, highlighting the life story experience outlined and interrelated within the context of the chapter. The idea of belonging, community, and integration is important in promoting understanding and feeling about living with other cultures and society and being apart from another ethnic group. I use the Listening Guide (LG) as a method for analysis of my data, the narrative as representing the life story interview experience in which participants shared life stories and their reflections and perspectives to the narrative as related to belonging, community, and integration.

It is important to understand living in other societies and cultures does not automatically happen. The process of belonging, community, and integration into the new society involved factors within the new society. The Kurdish refugee background

experience and knowledge have certainly played a role as factors facilitating them into the new society and culture because belonging, community, and ingratiation knowledge have important and powerful positions for Kurdish refugees in the new society. Refugees often are isolated from the new society because of a lack of language skills and knowledge resources, exemplified by the Kurds in Finland who have difficulties finding a job because of insufficient education level and language skills. Those disadvantages are related to isolating them from the community in which they are living. According to the Kurdish refugee life story interview experience, Kurdish refugees have difficulty in their educational background and classroom access for a variety of reasons in their origin countries.

Based on participants' life story experiences and research studies relevant to the research study, maintaining the right values of own belonging and community and attempting to get to understand and know a new culture and society provides the best conditions for coexistence and integration for refugees and migrants. The learning of a new language and education level have a link to acculturation construction for the refugees and helps develop social capital competencies for belonging, community and integration in the new country. Belonging and community is an intent of "seeking" and "accepting" in a Kurdish refugee context for identifying and constructing a new life through positive interactions.

Most of the Kurds who were forced to flee their home country were very young and inexperienced and, because of the political and social conflict in the Kurdistan areas, they could not access the information and awareness needed. Therefore, they need support and protection in the host country to find their rightful place in the new country.

The Kurdish people who participated in my research project shared their experiences pertaining to war and disturbances in the Kurdistan region and, because of such adverse circumstances, the majority of these individuals' faced challenges in accessing higher academic education. Basic education is one of the fundamental rights of each individual in society. The responses to data collocation during this study brought to light the unjust neglect of human rights in Kurdistan areas.

According to the interviewees, the majority of study participants decided to study in the host country; however, due to various reasons, this was not possible. The Kurds always have trouble introducing themselves, because Kurdistan is not recognised as

an independent state and, as such, they have to introduce themselves in the form of a Persian, Turkish or Arab. These interactions affect the mental health and emotional condition of the personality of the Kurdish people.

The Kurdish refugees experienced many stressful events and the associated trauma of those events which caused them to flee and leave their home country. Based on participants' experiences, some of them faced imprisonment, torture, malnutrition, physical assault, extreme fear, and rape before being forced to flee. Kurdish refugees during the asylum-seeking process encountered separation from family members and close friends, which caused both emotional and physical pain, and they were forced to tolerate very unpleasant environmental conditions.

Exploring the complex connotations of belonging, community, and integration by learning a language, education, acculturation, and social capital is found to remain an essential versatile idea in the refugee context and the feeling of positively existing in a new country.

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